

MAYNOOTH UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The issues surrounding gender-based violence (GBV) in Ireland have been outlined in the Second National Strategy on Domestic, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence 2016-2021 and the National Strategy for Women and Girls 2017. Within the higher education sector, the statutory planning and development body for higher education, the Higher Education Authority (HEA), together with direction from the state, developed and launched in 2019 a National Framework *Safe, Respectful, Supportive and Positive: Ending Sexual Violence and Harassment in Irish Higher Education Institutions Framework*. It is a roadmap and toolkit of strategies and policies to be embedded in the duty of care for students and staff in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and research organisations (DES, 2019). Funding was provided to HEIs to support the creation of institutional policies and strategies to implement the National Framework. As a follow-up, on 4 August 2020, Simon Harris, Minister for Further Education and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, issued a directive to all HEIs to develop and publish, on their institutional websites, by February 2021, a specific institutional action plan, on tackling sexual violence and harassment within their institution. In order to measure the prevalence of GBV in Irish HEIs Minister Harris announced the launch of a National Staff and Student Survey on Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment in Higher Education Institutions. This survey was conducted by the HEA in April 2021. It was sent to the entire higher education staff and student population of 39,000 staff and 235,000 students in order to create a robust evidence base for further policy decisions. Each HEI will receive their individual results.

The Irish Universities Association (IUA) created policy Guidance for universities advising that institutional arrangements should be situated within a broader institutional context that focuses on prevention, support, and an institutional culture that promotes the values of respect, dignity, and integrity (IUA, 2019).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

In response to the national imperative to end GBV in Irish HEIs, Maynooth University (MU) responded in the following ways:

- It formed a working group to implement the 2019 National Framework;
 - It created an institutional Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment 2021–2024;
 - It created a policy oversight group and operational/implementation group to manage the policy;
- MU Equality & Diversity Policy 2018;
- MU Protect Staff against Workplace Bullying 2008. This policy is currently being upgraded to include Anti-Bullying & Harassment, Sexual Harassment and Sexual Misconduct in the workplace with a similar policy specifically for students;
- Gender Identity & Gender Expression Policy 2020;

This is a set of policies with a mix of GBV-focused policies and broader policies addressing the issue as one of its parts.

MU Intersectionality Working Group, led by the equality officer has been established as part of MU's work with the Athena SWAN Charter.

URLs

- › Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment - Maynooth University: <https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/edi/edi-projects/consent-framework>
- › Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy: https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/sites/default/files/assets/document/Equality%20and%20Diversity%20Policy%20-%202018%20FINAL_1.pdf
- › Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment and Sexual Harassment: https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/sites/default/files/assets/document/Policy%20%26%20Procedures%20for%20the%20Protection%20of%20Staff%20Against%20Workplace%20Bullying%20%20Harassment%20%26%20Sexual%20Harassment_0.pdf
- › Gender Identity and Expression Policy: https://www.maynoothuniversity.ie/sites/default/files/assets/document/Gender%20Identity%20and%20Expression%20Policy_2.pdf

Entry into force:

- Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment – Maynooth University (MU): 2021
- Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy: 2018
- Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment and Sexual Harassment: 2008
- Gender Identity and Expression Policy: 2018.

TRAINING

As part of the Action Plan, MU adopted the Active Consent Programme workshops, and online Bystander Intervention Programmes are being offered to all students and staff. The Bystander Intervention programme was supposed to roll out in 2021 (UCC, 2019), but due to the pandemic it

was initiated in early 2022, led by the Equality, Diversity, Inclusion and Interculturalism Office, the Department of Law, the Maynooth Students Union, and the Office of the Dean of Teaching and Learning, Clubs and Societies.

Among the priorities listed in the Equality and Diversity Policy is making training on equality and diversity issues available to all staff as part of wider programmes from induction, recruitment, and selection through to management, development and leadership.

The Protection of Staff Policy foresees the provision of training for people managers in dealing with complaints of bullying, harassment, sexual harassment, and victimisation.

The Gender Identity and Expression Policy establishes that Human Resources will provide training for people managers in dealing with complaints of bullying, harassment, sexual harassment, and victimisation.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

MU is a leading research university, particularly in the social sciences, and is guided by national research and innovation priorities and the grand challenges identified by the EU and the UN Sustainable Development Goals. In relation to GBV, MU in partnership with Trinity College Dublin (TCD) researched and published a study on the prevalence of sexual violence and its effects in Ireland in December 2020 (MU, 2020), which was significant as it was the first Irish prevalence survey in a decade.

MU developed the National Gender Equality Dashboard for HEIs that was launched by Minister Harris in March 2021. The dashboard offers a valuable baseline from which progress on gender equality can be visualised and measured across all grades of staff in HEIs¹. Maynooth University staff participated in the Citizens' Assembly on Gender Equality² meeting on gender-based and domestic violence on 13 March 2021. They presented an analysis of the pervasive and prevalent nature of GBV as well as of Covid-19 as being a catalyst in advancing GBV.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The four policies combined address **seven** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, stalking, organisational violence, online violence and other (gender-based bullying).

The two GBV-focused policies refer to sexual violence, sexual and gender-based harassment, stalking, organisational violence, gender-based bullying including their online forms, while the other two policies, which are not GBV-focused, refer to sexual and gender-based harassment and bullying.

¹ MU. (2021, March 8). Minister Simon Harris Launches National Gender Equality Dashboard for HEIs. (M. U. Press, Producer) Retrieved July 13, 2021, from Maynooth University: www.maynoothuniversity.ie/research/research-news-events/latest-news/minister-simon-harris-launches-national-gender-equality-dashboard-heis

² The Citizens' Assembly on Gender Equality was established by Oireachtas resolution in July 2019 to consider gender equality and make recommendations to the Oireachtas to advance gender equality. Link to the GBV meeting: <https://www.citizensassembly.ie/en/previous-assemblies/2020-2021-citizens-assembly-on-gender-equality/news-publications/press-releases/citizens-assembly-to-meet-on-the-topic%20A0gender-based-violence.html>

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The four policies combined cover all **7Ps** – namely, prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnerships and policies.

All four policies refer to prevention, provision of services, and partnerships. The Action Plan also covers prevalence. The Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment and Sexual Harassment Policy covers prosecution and also refers to protection. The Gender Identity and Expression Policy also addresses prevention.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment

Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy

Gender Identity and Expression Policy

Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment and Sexual Harassment

All policies target **academic and non-academic staff**. Most of them, except for the Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment, and Sexual Harassment Policy, also target **students**.

The Equality and Diversity Policy also applies to applicants, visitors, customers, clients, third-party service providers, and contractors, and it relates to the services the university provides while carrying out its activities, whether internally or externally.

The Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment, and Sexual Harassment Policy relates to bullying, harassment, and sexual harassment not only by fellow employees, but also by clients, customers, or other business contacts with whom an employee might reasonably expect to come into contact in the course of his or her employment. The policy applies to employees and non-employees both in the workplace and at work-associated events such as meetings, conferences, and work-related social events, whether on or off the campus.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policies altogether cover **three vulnerable groups and one other group**. The Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy addresses staff with the temporary contracts and others, including Maynooth University

visitors, customers, clients, third party service providers and contractors, and relates to the services we provide while carrying out our activities, whether internally or externally. The Gender Identity and Expression Policy addresses LGBTQIA+ staff and students.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Gender Identity and Expression Policy and subsequent guidelines aim to provide a standard around supporting transgender and gender diverse students and staff. Detailed processes for accessing formal recognition of gender within the university systems and where to access personal support will be outlined in the Gender Identity

and Expression Guidelines. As transgender and gender diverse students and staff are vulnerable to bullying, harassment, and sexual harassment, this policy is intended to inform staff, students, and the university community of the protocol for ensuring the respect and dignity of this group of individuals.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment tackles the issue of bystanders via the Bystander Intervention Training for Staff and Students which is being developed in line with bystander intervention for all discriminatory and prejudicial behaviours.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment, and Sexual Harassment policy and the Gender Identity and Expression Policy address the role of perpetrators.

Perpetrators are mentioned in relation to the procedure that follows non-compliance with the policy. The respondent will be given every reasonable opportunity to respond to allegations. He or she has a right to be appropriately accompanied while being interviewed. An appropriate accompanying person may be a union representative or an employee of the university of the

respondent's choice. The accompanying person may not be a witness to the investigation. The committee will explain that the investigation must follow fair procedures, ensuring that the rights of the complainant and the respondent are protected. The respondent will be informed that the investigation is confidential to the greatest extent consistent with the requirements of a full, fair, and comprehensive investigation and that this confidentiality should be respected. In this regard, the respondent will be informed that he or she should not discuss the case with any other party to the investigation or otherwise share any information in relation to the case.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment addresses indicators relating to prevalence, prevention, protection, provision of services, and partnership:

- Prevalence: Success Indicator – the development of an online reporting tool; reporting to the HEA annually.
- Prevention: Success Indicator – the ongoing dissemination of information on the Action Plan and the Consent Workshops to students and staff;
- Protection: Success Indicator – students and staff know where to report complaints and are aware of the process involved. Incoming students have an understanding of what students can do to foster a culture of respect and zero tolerance of sexual harassment and sexual misconduct and what the university expects from them in relation to positive and respectful behaviours. All students have been offered an Active Consent Workshop or other healthy relationship workshops;
- Provision of Services: Success Indicator – student counselling services, the anonymous reporting tool is fit for purpose and in line with latest developments; staff in student services and frontline staff will be given training in providing trauma-informed support to students;
- Partnerships: Success Indicator – positive engagement with external experts and organisations to inform on the implementation of the National Consent Framework.

The Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy also developed indicators. However, there are only general indicators and these do not relate specifically to GBV.

Monitoring: Yes. The Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment monitors the number of cases and the results of the institutional procedure while the Gender Identity and Expression Policy focuses on the results of the institutional procedure.

Evaluation: Yes. The Action Plan to Tackle Sexual Violence and Harassment provides for evaluation. All data are collected, evaluated and presented to the Governing Authority and the HEA annually as per the National Imperative to Report Findings to the HEA.

Maynooth University Equality and Diversity Policy has a Review and Reporting system. However, there are only general tasks and these do not relate specifically to GBV.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Protection of Staff against Workplace Bullying, Harassment, and Sexual Harassment Policy sets up a step-by-step reporting and investigation **procedure for all**.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, timeframe, responsible persons.

This procedure applies to bullying, harassment, and sexual harassment committed not only by fellow employees, but also by clients, customers, or other business contacts with whom an employee might reasonably expect to come into contact in the course of his or her employment. The policy applies to employees and non-employees both in the workplace and at work-associated events such as meetings, conferences, and work-related social events, whether on or off the campus. If a staff member wishes to report an incident of bullying, harassment, or sexual harassment, there are three types of procedure that can be used. These are: informal procedures, mediation, and formal procedures. Usually, the process will begin with informal procedures and, if the case is resolved using informal procedures, it will end there. If the complaint is not resolved, the university will offer mediation, if appropriate, as a means of examining and resolving the complaint. If mediation is used and is successful in resolving the complaint, the process will end there. If the complaint is not resolved to the satisfaction of the complainant using informal procedures or mediation, or both, or if the complainant does not wish to use those procedures, the university will, at the request of the complainant, use formal procedures (interviews are conducted with the complainant, the respondent, and any witnesses).

If the complainant or the respondent is unhappy with the outcome of the procedure, either party can appeal to the secretary of the Human Resources Committee not later than two weeks after receiving the decision of the Investigation Committee. The person appealing the outcome of the procedure shall set out the reason for the appeal in writing. The secretary of the Human Resources Committee, having received proper notification of appeal, shall refer the matter to the president who will appoint an officer of the university who has not been involved in the process to date to hear the appeal. This officer will make a recommendation on the appeal to the president, whose decision on the matter will be final.

Responsible persons: The Director of Human Resources is responsible for the reporting and investigation procedure.

Timeframe: It is highly desirable that the suggested timeframes be adhered to. However, there may be circumstances where the timeframe may need to be altered. This is in consultation with the parties concerned in the investigation.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Nadine Shinkwin in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

